

≡ **TITLE: DEVELOPMENT OF A BENCH-SCALE TWO-STAGE PROCESS FOR BIOGAS PRODUCTION FROM SWINE WASTE EFFLUENT**

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□ **DURATION:**

October 2012 – June 2013

□ **ABSTRACT**

A two-stage bioreactor system consisting of two 30-L plastic drum digesters connected in series was setup and batch-fed with organic load of: 17% organic swine manure, 30% fresh inoculum, and 53% water. The hydraulic retention time (HRT) for digester 1 was 6-8 days; digester 2 was 13-16 days. Using principal component analysis (PCA), we showed that the top 5 bioprocess parameters were total solids (TS), total suspended solids (TSS), chemical oxygen demand (COD), biochemical oxygen demand (BOD), and volume of gas. Significant positive correlations were observed with TS, TSS, COD, and BOD; volume of gas was negatively correlated and increased twice compared to digester 1. Three of the parameters namely: TS, TSS, BOD exhibited significant % reduction. Data clustering was also observed. The bioprocess efficiency for the two-stage reactors was computed to be 73.89%. The average gas volumetric production rates were 15.875 L/ L Reactor1 or 30.45 L/ L Reactor2. Based on the cumulative gas production, the theoretical Biochemical Methane Potential (BMP) on the average was 880.2289×10^3 ml CH₄/g COD, which represented only about half of the methane value.

□ *OBJECTIVES:*

To develop a bench-scale 20-liter biogas production using a two-stage process and determine the operational process parameters.

□ *SIGNIFICANCE:*

In the Philippines, an estimated national amount of swine manure production of about 44,478 tons per day or 16.23 M tons per year would require sustainable waste disposal technology. The two-stage digestion is a process configuration using separate reactors, one for liquefaction (hydrolysis) and acidification and the other for biomethanation. The primary source of microbial inoculum will be from manure slurry. The concept of two-phase digestion (Pohland and Ghosh 1971) also known as acid phase digestion involves a first phase that is usually operated at a short hydraulic retention time with a lower pH while methane formation stage is operated at a long hydraulic retention times (10-30 days) at a near neutral pH to maintain favorable conditions for methanogenic bacterial. Process stabilization will be maintained by various bio-physicochemical parameters.

The waste management of manure will mitigate greenhouse gasses (GHG) from livestock and could increase the profitability of production systems using enhanced methane production and thus will provide a cost effective alternative renewable energy source for clean fuel.

Although considered in the niche market (Teune B, Orprecio J et al. 2010), together with landfill gasification and banana-waste to biomethane, it is considered to be the cleanest, more efficient and most-climate neutral transport fuel in the market (EU well-to-wheel study, 2011).

The relatively high cost of methane digesters fabrication is still a barrier and a challenge to find and use low cost materials and process for this conversion remains an option to be considered in the application of micro-bioprocessing in renewable clean fuel production and waste management.

□ *REVIEW OF LITERATURE*

Currently, the majority of the world energy needs are supplied through carbon-containing fossil fuel sources such as coal, natural gas, and oil. Due to the economic conditions escalating oil prices and negative environmental impacts, government initiatives in many countries are focusing on the increased use of various renewable energies including solar, wind, biomass, hydro-power, tidal energy, and energy from waste.

Over 1.8 billion tonnes of waste including households, industry and agriculture, etc. are generated each year in Europe alone. Biogas production from waste provides an environmentally friendly way for waste management as well as production of sustainable renewable energy.

(Usable biogas potential in Germany, FNR 2008; Cited in Weiland 2010)

Anaerobic digestion (AD) using manure for biogas production is one of the most promising uses of biomass wastes because it provides a source of energy while simultaneously resolving ecological and agrochemical issues. Depending on the feedstock, the biogas produced from anaerobic digestion of waste usually contains 40-70% methane (CH_4) and 30-50% carbon dioxide (CO_2).

The basic reasons to process manure to biogas using anaerobic digestion (AD) are as follows: The first reason is to recover useable energy that contributes no net carbon to the atmosphere. A second reason to use AD for biogas is to reduce the risk from pathogens. A third and prospective benefit from AD processing of manure is the potential to recover nutrients from digestate, leaving a disposable water stream.

Studies of Møller et al., (2004) found that at 15°C , aerobic processes in the surface layers of the stored manure slurry are more dominant than anaerobic processes, while at a higher temperature (20°C), the aerobic and anaerobic processes are of almost equal importance. In general, the anaerobic processes are more dominant during storage of cattle manure than during storage of pig manure.

Small scale anaerobic digesters provide potential wealth of benefits and solution to: a) poor indoor air quality and subsequent chronic health problems, b) unequal exposure to

hazards by gender, c) the need for a cooking fuel, d) deforestation for fuel use, e) lack of treatment of animal waste, f) expensive inorganic fertilizers, g) mitigation of methane released into the atmosphere, and h) reduced amount of residuals for disposal, compared with aerobic treatment. However, many small scale anaerobic digesters in developing countries fail for various reasons, including: design, high capital cost, construction, maintenance, user needs, operational problems, or availability of materials for maintenance.

The anaerobic process begins with a group of fermentative bacteria that excrete enzymes that break down macromolecules in the reactor. Next, a different group of fermentative bacteria partially oxidizes the organic acids produced during fermentation into volatile fatty acids (with less than two carbons) in a process called acidogenesis. The volatile fatty acids of significance formed in this step are: propionic acid, n-butyric acid, and isobutyric acid. Alcohol formation also takes place during this step.

Hydrogen-producing acetogenic bacteria convert the volatile fatty acids and ethanol produced in acidogenesis into acetic acid, hydrogen, and carbon dioxide in a process called acetogenesis. In order for acetogenesis to be a thermodynamically favorable process and for the reaction to proceed in a forward direction, the partial pressure of hydrogen in the system must be less than 10^{-3} atm. Hydrogen is scavenged by methanogenic archaea which, in turn, results in a low partial pressure of hydrogen and maintains a thermodynamically favorable acetogenesis process.

Methane (CH_4) production, which is an H_2 -consuming reaction requires a reduction in the level of H_2 partial pressure to drive the reaction forward. In anaerobic digestion the bioconversion of fatty acids, such as propionate stops when the H_2 concentration is above 10^{-4} atm; higher H_2 concentrations can result in increased concentrations of propionic acid and other carboxylic acids in the digester. Increased acid concentration can cause the pH to decrease and inhibit or stop CH_4 production.

Methane fermentation is a complex process, which can be divided up into four phases: hydrolysis, acidogenesis, acetogenesis/dehydrogenation, and methanation. The individual degradation steps are carried out by different consortia of microorganisms requirements on the environment. A complex consortium of microorganisms participates in the hydrolysis and fermentation of organic material. Most of the bacteria are strict anaerobes such as *Bacteriocides*, *Clostridia*, and *Bifidobacteria*. Furthermore, some facultative anaerobes such as Streptococci and Enterobacteriaceae take part. The higher volatile fatty acids are converted into acetate and hydrogen by obligate hydrogen-producing acetogenic bacteria. The hydrogen-producing acetogenic bacteria are not well characterized. Typical homoacetogenic bacteria are *Acetobacterium woodii* and *Clostridium aceticum*. The accumulation of hydrogen can inhibit the metabolism of the acetogenic bacteria. The maintenance of an extremely low partial pressure of hydrogen is, therefore, essential for the acetogenic and H_2 -producing bacteria. Although many microbial details of metabolic networks in a methanogenic consortium are not clear, present knowledge suggests that hydrogen may be a limiting substrate for methanogens. This assumption is based on the fact that addition of H_2 -

producing bacteria to the natural biogas-producing consortium increases the daily biogas production. At the end of the degradation chain, two groups of methanogenic bacteria produce methane from acetate or hydrogen and carbon dioxide. These bacteria are strict anaerobes and require a lower redox potential for growth than most other anaerobic bacteria. Only few species are able to degrade acetate into CH_4 and CO_2 , e.g., *Methanosarcina barkeri*, *Metanococcus mazei*, and *Methanotrix soehngenii*, whereas all methanogenic bacteria are able to use hydrogen to form methane.

Much is known about the basic metabolism in different types of anaerobic digestion processes, but little is known about the microbes responsible for these processes. Only few percent of bacteria and archaea have so far been isolated, but little is known about the dynamics and interactions between these microorganisms. The lack of knowledge results sometimes in malfunctions and unexplainable failures of biogas fermenters. With molecular techniques, more information can be received about the community structures in anaerobic processes. A recent report detected 68 taxonomic groups of methanogens in samples from ten agricultural biogas plants. This showed that hydrogenotrophic methanogens dominate in most agricultural biogas plants. A high share of acetogenic methanogens can be found obviously only in biogas plants which are operated at low ammonia concentrations.

Research literature showed that methanogenic diversity is lower in plants operating at thermophilic temperatures. Although the growth rate of methanogenic bacteria is higher at thermophilic process temperatures, these processes are more sensitive to temperature fluctuations and require longer time to adapt to a new temperature. Furthermore, these result in a larger degree of imbalance and a higher risk for ammonia inhibition. Mesophilic bacteria tolerate temperature fluctuations of ± 3 °C without significant reductions in methane production. An option for thermophilic digester is to load to a higher degree or operate at a lower hydraulic retention time (HRT).

Methane formation takes place within a relatively narrow pH interval, from about 6.5 to 8.5 with an optimum interval between 7.0 and 8.0. The process is severely inhibited if the pH decreases below 6.0 or rises above 8.5.

Acetic acid is usually present in higher concentration than other fatty acids, but propionic and butyric acids are more inhibitory to methanogens. This inhibition is associated with the un-dissociated form. Thus, the inhibiting effect of VFAs is much higher in systems of low pH value.

Methane can be generated via two different pathways during methanogenesis. One pathway takes the substrates hydrogen and carbon dioxide and forms methane through hydrogenotrophic methanogenesis. Some of the hydrogen and carbon dioxide is converted into acetate through homoacetogenesis. The remaining pathway converts acetate into methane and carbon dioxide in a process called acetotrophic methanogenesis.

Why do we study the two-stage anaerobic digestion process? Recent reports showed that methane yields and production were shown to be higher in the two-stage reactors than in the one-stage reactor, however results of the continuous experiments showed lower yields than those obtained in batch conditions (Bertin et al. 2013) and as suggested (Llansing et al. 2010) seasonal producers could utilize low-cost digesters operating at a lower temperature range of 24 to 26°C and sustained at 50–78% of normal methane production levels for 75 days at a co-digestion.

This concept of two-phase digestion is also known as acid phase digestion. The first phase is usually operated at a short SRT (4-12hr) and at lower pH (≤ 6), while methane formation stage is operated at long SRTs (10-30 days) and at neutral pH to maintain favorable environment for methanogenic bacteria.

Pohland and Ghosh (1971) first proposed the physical separation of the process into an acidogenic and a methanogenic stage. This provides enhanced stability to the different groups of microorganisms for better process control, and to extract more net energy from the system. In a single-stage anaerobic digestion process, a variety of higher organic acids, such as propionic, butyric, and lactic, as well as alcohols and ketones, are formed during the breakdown of the organic substrates by acidogens. However, in a well operated process, these products are mostly converted to acetic acid and hydrogen, which, in turn, are converted to methane gas. On the other hand, in a two-stage anaerobic digestion process, the end products from acidification stage are usually ideal for anaerobic treatment with high VFAs concentrations. It was suggested that HRT of 3 days is needed for activated sludge achieving the optimum acidogenic fermentation in the two-phase anaerobic digestion.

It is known that in a methane reactor, 67% of the methane is produced by acetate-utilizing methanogens and 33% is produced by hydrogenophilic methanogens. ethanol that are not as favourable as acetate for methane production. Various authors achieved more than 10% increase in methane production using a two-stage process compared to a single-stage. Despite their higher loading rates, improved process stability and flexibility, there are relatively few commercial two-stage anaerobic digestion units.

There are some disadvantages to the anaerobic digestion process. First, small scale anaerobic digestion requires the addition of water, which is limiting especially during the dry season. Anaerobic digestion takes more time to start-up the process because methanogens have slower growth kinetics. High effluent BOD₅ concentrations prevent direct discharge into water bodies. Anaerobic digestion may require the addition of alkalinity (in the form of sodium bicarbonate) to reach levels of 2000- 3000 mg/L as CaCO₃ in order to maintain an optimal pH. Reaction rates in the anaerobic digestion processes are much more sensitive to changes in temperature. For this reason, a stable operating temperature is very important, and changes in temperature of less than 0.5 °C/day are recommended. Higher capital costs are associated with anaerobic digestion than with aerobic treatment because a larger reactor volume is required for anaerobic treatment and because of the additional infrastructure required for methane capture and energy use. Anaerobic digestion is much more vulnerable to upsets from

toxic compounds found in the waste stream and there is a potential for the production of corrosive gases and odors. Also, the theoretical higher biogas yields are limited since the acidogenic phase separation prevents the hydrogen to methane pathway.

For anaerobic digestion to be cost-competitive, the minimum waste chemical oxygen demand (COD) should be above 1500 to 2000 mg/L. However, the process performance such as methane yield, solids reduction efficiency primarily depends on the level of biodegradable organics in the waste, or biochemical oxygen demand (BOD). The most common anaerobic bioreactor designs that provide biomass retention (thereby preventing failure of digester) are the upflow anaerobic sludge bed (UASB), expanded granular sludge bed (EGSB), fluidized bed bioreactor (FBR), and anaerobic membrane bioreactor (AnMBR).

A general scheme for anaerobic digestion process is shown below.

Anaerobic Digestion Process Diagram. (after Grady et al., 2009).

Gas storage must be available for the liquid volume change in anaerobic digestion to prevent exposure to flammable volatiles and avoid accidents. It is recommended that the volume in the reactor for gas storage space should be 1/5 the volume of the solid and liquid volume in the reactor. Biogas storage containers should be durable and resistant to corrosion. If methane gas is released uncontrolled, methane and air can form an explosive mixture that can spontaneously combust at high temperatures (Tchobanoglous et al., 2003).

Methane yield can be expressed in several ways. The term “methane productivity” is used to indicate the yield of methane per unit of a variable term such as volatile solids (VS) destroyed, VS loaded, volume or animal production. Methane productivity measured in terms of VS destroyed corresponds to the theoretical methane yield (Bu) by a complete degradation of all organics in the manure. The theoretical methane potential can be calculated from Bushwell’s formula (Symons and Bushwell, 1933). Methane productivity in terms of VS loaded is referred to as the ultimate methane yield (Bo). The ultimate methane yield will always be lower than the theoretical yield due to the fact that because a fraction of the substrate is used to synthesize bacterial mass, a fraction of the organic material will be lost in the effluent, and lignin-containing compounds are only degraded to a limited degree. Inhibition of the biological process by inhibitors such as ammonia and VFA is another factor which means that the methane yield is reduced, compared with the yield which would be produced if inhibition was not present. It has been observed that both the ultimate methane yield (Bo) and the volumetric methane production from manure of different origin can be very variable. For practical purposes, bioprocess efficiency is based on the removal rates of Total Suspended Solids (TSS). This is based on the observation that common wastewater treatment processes are designed to remove TSS and not TS.

Some factors affecting performance are as follows:

A number of factors are important in the operation of an anaerobic digester, including: hydraulic retention time, solids retention time (also known as mean cell residence time), organic loading rate, mixing, pH, alkalinity, temperature, pH, and reactor gas production.

Suggested Operation Parameters for Rural Developing World

Applications

Operation Parameters		Source(s)
SRT min	4	(Tchobanoglous et al., 2003)
lim (d)		
Safety Factor (SF)	10 30	(Rittmann & McCarty, 2001)
SRT (d)	20 70	(Garfi et al., 2011)
pH	6.6 - 7.6	(Tchobanoglous et al., 2003)
OLR (kg VS/(d*m ³))	1.0 - 3.5	(Sharma & Pellizzi, 1991)

Hydraulic retention time, θ (days), is defined as the average amount of time one reactor volume of actively digesting sludge stays within the reactor.

$$\theta = \frac{V}{Q}$$

where: θ = hydraulic retention time (d)

V = volume of reactor (m³)

Q = influent flow rate

Where there is no recycling HRT is equal to SRT (Solid Retention Time)

Hydraulic retention time is important to reactor operation and design because it defines the length of time the substrate and particular constituents targeted for removal will be in contact with the biomass within the reactor. Reaction kinetics of methanogenesis and fermentation are the rate-limiting kinetics in anaerobic digestion. Most often, methanogenesis is the rate-limiting step. At temperatures close to 30 °C, SRT's 20 to 30 days are recommended. It is important to design reactors for sufficient retention times so that volatile solids destruction can take place.

In biological wastewater treatment, large scale reactors are designed with *safety factors* for various reasons, including: the lack of operator oversight, variability of waste water stream, and fluctuations in operating conditions. Safety factors in biological treatment systems are different from safety factors used in structures. The minimum SRT, or the SRT at which washout occurs is multiplied by a safety factor. (Washout is the point at which the growth of the microorganisms contained in the reactor is less than the loss of cells in the reactor effluent. There is a no net loss of cells in the system.) Because the minimum SRT is the borderline of system failure, it is important to have a large safety factor. Specifically, in rural areas of developing countries, there will be fluctuations in various parameters. A Safety Factor of 10 is used in the semi-empirical kinetic model.

Mixing is another important parameter to consider in the design of an anaerobic digester. Mixing increases the rate kinetics of anaerobic digestion, accelerating the biological conversion process. Additionally, mixing allows uniform heating of the reactor. Mixing can be done mechanically through motorized impellers or turbines within the reactor or pneumatically by injecting gas (in anaerobic digestion, methane and carbon dioxide gas) via spargers at the bottom of the reactor.

The *pH* of the digester is yet another important parameter in anaerobic digestion. The pH should be maintained between 6.6 and 7.6. One difficulty is maintaining pH above 6.6. During digester start-up, overloading, or instability, organic acids are intermediate products produced by the microorganisms. The presence of too high a concentration of organic acids decreases the pH, decreases methane production, and can cause reactor souring or reactor failure. The carbonic acid system dominates pH control most of the time in anaerobic digestion.

Alkalinity is defined as the capacity of water to neutralize acid. In anaerobic digestion, the normal percentage of carbon dioxide in the gas phase is 25 – 45 %.

Because bacterial growth is mediated by a complex set of enzymatic chemical reactions and the reaction rate of all chemical reactions depends on *temperature*, bacterial growth rate depends on temperature. As a general rule, bacterial growth rates double for each 10°C rise in temperature over a temperature range, which varies by bacterial species. For mesophilic anaerobic digestion, the operational temperature range is 10 to 30°C. The operational temperature range for thermophilic anaerobic digestion is 55 to 65°C. Specific methane production rates are 50 to 100 percent higher for thermophilic anaerobic digestion than for mesophilic anaerobic digestion.

Gas production is measured using a flow-through gas meter and used in the calculation of the volumetric gas production (L gas/ L vol of Digester).

□ **EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE**

Set-up of Bench-Scale Digesters

Batch reactors (Digesters 1 & 2, each at 30-liter capacity) were assembled from two plastic drums with cover. The PVC stirrer was fabricated having a Ø (diameter) of ½” and ¾” with acrylic sheet (5 mm thick x 2” x 8”) connected to a Ø ½” PVC pipe, serving as paddle of the stirrer with gas outlet for each reactor. The two bioreactor-drums were connected in series by a 1/2” pipe. Sampling ports were installed in each reactor with ½” PVC pipes and PV ball valves.

Configuration of a Two-stage Digester and Organic Feed Digestate

During the first-stage, Digester 1 was loaded with organic waste, fresh inoculum and water to a volume of 20 L. The hydrolysis-acidogenesis-acetogenesis reactor, Digester 1 was operated as a continuous stirred tank reactor for the Hydraulic Retention Time (HRT) of 6-8 days, at temperature of 34 to 35 °C, pH of 6.5 to 6.8. For the second stage, Digester 2 was fed with the effluent from the Digester 1 (after 8 days). Digester 2 was “optimized” for methanogenesis at an HRT of 13-16 days, with the same temperature (see Digester 1), at pH of 7.0 – 7.5 and stirred occasionally. Organic feed load of the Digester consisted by weight of: 17% organic swine manure, 30% fresh inoculum, and 53% water.

Determination of Water Quality and Bioprocess parameters

The influent and the effluent samples for each of the Digesters were analyzed for pH, temperature, chemical oxygen demand (COD), biological oxygen demand, total solids, total suspended solids (volatile solids VS), using standard methods (APHA, 1995). COD was measured using the DRB 200 Reactor while BOD₅ was determined using the Oxitap apparatus. Gas volume was measured using a gas meter, Flow Stream® Laminar Mass Flow Meters purchased locally.

Determination of Bioprocess Efficiency

Because common wastewater treatment processes are designed to remove TSS and not TS, total solids in treated effluent generally vary depending on the total solids of the influent. However, treated effluent TS results may actually be greater than influent TS due to chemical addition in the plant which may add TS to the wastewater. The removal rate or efficiency is calculated as a percentage as follows:

$$\{[\text{Influent} - \text{Effluent}] / \text{Influent}\} \times 100 = \% \text{ Removal}$$

Gas Heating Values

We did not experimentally determine the calorific or gas heating values of the biogas produced since we have developed this two-stage digester based on a bioprocess scale. The heating value of a gas is defined as the thermal energy per unit volume of the gas. It is expressed in Btu/ft³. For natural gas, it is approximately in the range of 900

to 1200 Btu/ft³. There are two heating values used in the industry. These are the lower heating value (LHV also termed as dry) or the net heating value and higher heating value (HHV also termed as wet) or the gross heating value. For a gas mixture, the term gross heating value is used. It is calculated based upon the heating values of the component gases and their mole fractions. This is the same as the thermodynamic heat of combustion since the enthalpy change for the reaction assumes a common temperature of the compounds before and after combustion. At roughly 60 percent methane, bio-gas possesses an energy content of 600 Btu/ ft³, which is similar to landfill gas. In Italy most of the biogas is obtained from organic waste present in landfills (Comino et al. 2009). For comparison, please see the table below for energy content of other sources.

Gas	Gross Heating Value		Net Heating Value	
	(Btu/ft ³)	(Btu/lb)	(Btu/ft ³)	(Btu/lb)
Hydrogen (H ₂)	325	61,084	275	51,628
Hydrogen Sulphide	672	7,479		
Landfill Gas	476			
Methane - CH ₄	1,011	23,811	910	21,433
	950	19,500	850	17,500
Natural Gas (typical)	-	-	-	-
	1,150	22,500	1,050	22,000

Energy Unit Conversion:

$$1 \text{ Btu/ft}^3 = 8.9 \text{ kcal/m}^3 = 3.73 \times 10^4 \text{ J/m}^3$$

$$1 \text{ Btu/lb} = 2,326.1 \text{ J/kg} = 0.55556 \text{ kcal/kg}$$

NOTE: A common method of relating HHV to LHV is:

$$\text{HHV} = \text{LHV} + \{h_v \times (n_{\text{H}_2\text{O, out}}/n_{\text{fuel, in}})\}$$

where h_v is the heat of vaporization of water, $n_{\text{H}_2\text{O, out}}$ is the moles of water vaporized and $n_{\text{fuel, in}}$ is the number of moles of fuel combusted.

Statistical Analysis

Statistical analyses were performed using available online Statistics and packages such as Kovach Computing Services; Multivariate Analysis for Principal Component Analysis and Clustering. T-test significance was compared with critical values for t -test at .05% probability distribution.

□ RESULTS

Tables 1 to 2 showed the results of bioprocess parameters for Reactor 1 and Reactor 2, which were operated in series without recirculation using a fed-batch process.. These parameters were monitored starting November (2012) to June (2013). Using t-test it was shown that % reduction in Total Solids (TS), Total Suspended Solids (TSS), Biochemical Oxygen Demand (BOD) were statistically significant (Please see Table 4). TS was reduced by 69.62%, TSS was reduced by 73.89%, and BOD was reduced by 78.65%; while Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) was reduced by 56.42%. The

average volume of gas production for the second Digester was almost doubled compared to the first Digester although remained non-significant. Figure 1 showed that the gas production was less at the start of the experiment on the months of November and December (2012). This was highest for the month of February and stabilized thereafter.

REACTOR 1								
TIME/ DURATION	PARAMETERS							
	pH	T (°C)	TS (mg/L)	TSS (mg/L)	COD (mg/L)	BOD (mg/L)	Vol of Gas (L)	HRT days
2012								
Nov	6.67	33	8,630	6,340	24,600	8,000	160	7
Dec	6.54	34	10,148	4,400	9,300	5,000	100	7
2013								
Jan	6.5	32	25,133	7,763	11,600	4,500	100	7
Feb	6.5	33	30,928	14,430	9,600	4,250	830	7
March	6.56	34	28,052	13,746	16,700	6,000	700	7
Apr	6.58	35	27,885	12,000	17,800	5,250	630	7
May	6.55	34	16,346.7	7,456.7	10,100	2,000	680	8
Jun	6.81	35	24,916	9,606	18,000	7,500	610	6

Table 1. Bioprocess parameters for Reactor 1.

REACTOR 2								
TIME/ DURATION	PARAMETERS							
	pH	T (°C)	TS (mg/L)	TSS (mg/L)	COD (mg/L)	BOD (mg/L)	Vol of Gas (L)	HRT days
2012								
Nov	7.10	33.8	7,365	3,313	11,000	2,500	460	14
Dec	7.03	33.	8,360	2,323	2,600	500	380	14
2013								
Jan	7.2	33	6,541	3,603	6,700	1,000	340	14
Feb	7.16	35	5,620	1,333	5,000	1,375	1,857	14
March	7.09	35	6,525	3,400	9,600	1,350	1,110	14
Apr	7.05	35	6,883	2,100	6,600	1,300	1,090	15
May	7.07	34	5,498	1,706.7	4,600	700	1,020	16
Jun	7.5	34	5,468	2,000	5,190	350	1,050	16

Table 2. Bioprocess parameters for Reactor 2.

TIME/ DURATION	REACTOR 1	REACTOR 2	% EFFICIENCY (REMOVAL RATE) {[Influent - Effluent] / Influent} x 100 = % Removal
	TSS (\bar{x}) (mg/L) -INFLUENT-	TSS (\bar{x}) (mg/L) -EFFLUENT-	
Nov-Jun	9467.7125	2472.3375	73.89%

Table 3. Bioprocess Efficiency.

The bioprocess efficiency of 74 % (Table 3) for the two-stage digestion was calculated from the removal rate of the TSS, based on the literature that common wastewater treatment processes were designed to remove TSS and not TS. (Treated effluent TS results may actually be greater than influent TS due to chemical addition in the plant.)

STATISTICAL SIGNIFICANCE OF BIOPROCESS PARAMETERS					
BIOPROCESS PARAMETERS	MEAN/ AVERAGE		% REDUCTIO N	Statistics <i>t</i> -test Obs	Statistical Significance Df=14 .05%; two-sided t value=4.14
	Reactor1	Reactor2			
Total Solids	21504.8375	6532.5	14972.3375/ \bar{x} 69.62%	4.89	<i>significant</i>
Total Suspended Solids	9467.7125	2472.3375	6995.375/ \bar{x} 73.89%	5.32	<i>significant</i>
COD	14712.5	6411.25	8301.25/ \bar{x} 56.42%	3.84	<i>not significant</i> (t obs lower)
BOD	5312.5	1134.375	4178.125/ \bar{x} 78.65%	5.85	<i>significant</i>
Vol Gas (L)	476.25	913.375	{191.78% increase}	2.09	<i>not significant</i>

Table 4. Statistical Analysis of the Bioprocess Parameters

TIME/ DURATION	Theoretical Maximum Cumulative Methane Gas (ml) [Total Gross]	COD removed (g)	BMP (Theoretical) (ml CH ₄ /g COD)
Nov	460,000	13.600	33.8235 x 10 ³
Dec	840,000	6.700	125.3731 x 10 ³
Jan	1,180,000	4.900	240.8163 x 10 ³
Feb	3,037,000	4.600	660.2174 x 10 ³
Mar	4,147,000	7.100	584.0845 x 10 ³
Apr	5,237,000	11.200	467.5893 x 10 ³
May	6,257,000	5.500	1137.6364 x 10 ³
Jun	7,307,000	8.30125	880.2289 x 10 ³

Table 5. Biochemical Methane Potential (Theoretical).

The volume of gas production was related to the biochemical methane potential (BMP). This BMP test can determine the methane yield of an organic matter substrate by anaerobic digestion under specific condition and media. It was initially developed in the seventies (Owen et al., 1979). This was based on a common parameter for waste characterization to determine the quantity of methane (ml methane/g COD removed) that the waste can potentially produce in anaerobic conditions. We calculated the theoretical BMP based on the maximum cumulative gas production divided by the amount of Chemical Oxygen Demand for a particular time interval. As shown in Table 5, the theoretical BMP was highest for the month of May 2013. However, this leveled off on the average of the total month-interval for the whole experiment. With 50% methane (Comino et al. 2009), this represented about half of the BMP.

Figure 1. Histogram of Gas Production.

PRINCIPAL COMPONENT ANALYSIS			
<i>(Log₁₀ transformed data; non-centered)</i>			
PCA case scores	Axis 1	Axis 2	Axis 3
<i>pH</i>	1.351	0.072	-0.022
<i>Temperature</i>	2.329	0.095	-0.031
<i>Total Solids</i>	6.137	-0.046	0.175
<i>Total Suspended Solids</i>	5.547	-0.156	0.142
<i>COD</i>	5.99	-0.049	-0.156
<i>BOD</i>	5.073	-0.35	-0.136
<i>Vol of Gas (L)</i>	4.105	0.609	-0.007
<i>Hydraulic Retention Time</i>	1.57	0.253	-0.066

Table 5. Principal Component Analysis.

Principal component analysis (of axis 1) showed the top 5 parameters important to our study namely: Total Solids, Total Suspended solids, COD, BOD, and volume of Gas.

CORRELATION ANALYSIS

	<i>Total</i>							
CORREL	pH	Temperature	Solids	TSS	COD	BOD	Vol of Gas (L)	HRT
pH	1.000	0.253	-0.761	-0.771	-0.574	-0.713	0.486	0.911
Temperature	0.253	1.000	-0.129	-0.118	0.009	-0.073	0.640	0.182
Total Solids	-0.761	-0.129	1.000	0.953	0.505	0.631	-0.243	-0.802
TSS	-0.771	-0.118	0.953	1.000	0.621	0.693	-0.262	-0.823
COD	-0.574	0.009	0.505	0.621	1.000	0.911	-0.411	-0.743
BOD	-0.713	-0.073	0.631	0.693	0.911	1.000	-0.473	-0.879
Vol of Gas (L)	0.486	0.640	-0.243	-0.262	-0.411	-0.473	1.000	0.506
HRT	0.911	0.182	-0.802	-0.823	-0.743	-0.879	0.506	1.000

	<i>Total</i>							
p Values	pH	Temperature	Solids	TSS	COD	BOD	Vol of Gas (L)	HRT
Temperature	0.345		0.633	0.663	0.973	0.788	0.008	0.499
Total Solids	0.001	0.633		0.000	0.046	0.009	0.365	0.000
TSS	0.000	0.663	0.000		0.010	0.003	0.327	0.000
COD	0.020	0.973	0.046	0.010		0.000	0.114	0.001
BOD	0.002	0.788	0.009	0.003	0.000		0.065	0.000
Vol of Gas (L)	0.056	0.008	0.365	0.327	0.114	0.065		0.046
HRT	0.000	0.499	0.000	0.000	0.001	0.000	0.046	

Table 6. Correlation Chart

Correlation analysis showed that TS, TSS, COD, and BOD were positively correlated with each other while Vol of gas was negatively correlated.

Figure 2. Box-Whiskers plot of important water parameters

The average gas volumetric production rates were 15.875 L/ L Reactor1 or 30.45 L/ L Reactor2. Compared to a pilot-scale of 128L (Comino et al. 2009) (with a vol factor of 4.266) producing biogas of 1919.7 l, which is 50% methane.

Figure 3. Cluster Analysis with UPGMA

Using "Unweighted Pair Group Method with Arithmetic Mean", (UPGMA) also known as average linkage clustering in Figure 3, data showed that results for BOD, COD, TSS and TS were clustered together, while gas volume, temperature, HRT and pH were clustered as another group.

CLUSTER ANALYSIS (Untransformed Data)

Figure 4. Cluster Analysis without transformation.

Cluster analyses shown in Figure 4 showed that bioprocess data were specific for a given Reactor type: 1 or 2. However, this association was not observed for the data on Nov or Dec 2012. Results for Reactor 1-Nov 2012 is distally connected with the rest of Reactor 1 results, while the parameters results for the month Dec 2012 showed divergence with the Reactor 1 closely clustering with the results for Reactor2; with the Reactor 2 closely clustering with the results for Reactor1.

□ *SUMMARY AND CONCLUSION*

The two-stage anaerobic digestion offered a technological advantage via a theoretical enhancement of methanogenesis, which was delimited at a second digester while precursors, which were primarily volatile fatty acids accumulated at an earlier stage in the first bioreactor. This could be applied for specific capture of energy gases such as methane from organic waste. Based on the bioprocess results covering November to June, five important bioprocess parameters were identified using PCA namely: Total Solids, Total Suspended Solids, COD, BOD and Volume of Gas. Statistically significant reduction rates were recorded for TS (69.62%), TSS (73.89%), and BOD (78.65%). These were within range of the baseline values prescribed by the Environment Management Bureau (EMB-DENR), which calls for 90% reduction or 2,000 of BOD for industrial effluent indicators. However, the effluent cannot be directly discharged to bodies of water due to pervasive TS, TSS, COD levels. These parameters were positively correlated while the volume of gas was negatively correlated since the volume increased twice compared to the first digester. Data clustering analysis showed that the data obtained from Digester 1 were distinct from the data gathered from Digester 2. The volumetric gas production were stable and increased especially on the first quarter of 2013. Our bench-scale two-stage process exhibited an efficiency of 73.9%. A theoretical biochemical methane potential was calculated based on the maximal cumulative methane gas volumes of Reactor 2, which represented only half of this value for methane.

□ *TECHNO-ECONOMIC DATA:*

Eco-technology drivers were favored in our technology to support green energy production and at the same time countered the effect of climate change; while converting waste into useful energy.

□ *SOCIO-ECONOMIC DATA:*

The described two-stage bioprocess technology could enhance social benefits such as in providing threshold incentives and livelihood to the rural community as well as a clean healthy environment since hazardous waste organic animal manure could be used as a raw material in this technology.

□ *RECOMMENDATION*

We recommend the determination of calorific or gas heating values in order to assess the energy conversion as applied to electricity generation, boilers, combined heat and power, etc.

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